

ROLL FORMING OF FIBRE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE SHEET

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ABSTRACT

The recent availability of continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic sheets has witnessed an increasing interest in mass production techniques using such materials. This paper details a study on Plytron™ sheets demonstrating the applicability of roll forming to such thermoplastic materials. Suitable manufacturing conditions have been established and the importance of the entry and exit temperatures in relation to the product quality is highlighted. Defects such as fibre wrinkling, buckling and spring-back are shown to be strongly dependent on roll schedule, fibre architecture and the cooling rate. A novel method of obtaining real time strain history in thermoplastic composites has also been introduced.

INTRODUCTION

Due to the relatively recent availability of continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic (FRTP) sheets a large amount of commercial interest has been generated for the development of low-cycle time manufacturing techniques. It is generally accepted that thermoplastic composites lend themselves to mass production methods, due to their ability to be "reshaped" simply by the application of heat and relatively low forces. The other benefits such as long shelf-life, ease of handling and the potential for recycling are also well recognised. However until manufacturing techniques have become more conducive to mass production, the benefits of FRTP composites are unlikely to be fully realised.

Recent efforts in forming FRTP sheets have centred on variations of pressure forming and diaphragm forming techniques [1-3]. Other methods have transposed standard sheet metal forming processes, such as matched die stamping [4] and incremental forming [5,6], to these materials. There is a recognised demand for the ability to produce long narrow profiles such as top-hat and channel sections from FRTP sheets. An obvious manufacturing method offering high production rates for such sections is the well known method of semi-continuous roll forming widely used in the sheet metal industry. It involves the passing of a flat metal strip through a succession of rolls arranged in tandem, progressively deforming the strip into the desired final cross-sectional shape [7], as shown in Figure 1. Whilst the practice of roll forming is well established, the deformation mechanism that involves three-dimensional bending and stretching, is not yet fully understood [8]. The authors believe that this process, with some modifications,

lends itself to be used in the production of narrow and wide profile FRTP composite sections and goes some way towards realising their full benefits.

Figure 1. A typical roll forming process[9]

Preliminary trials into roll forming of FRTP composites have been reported by Cattanaach [10] but the degree of success and the detailed methodology of these trials remain unpublished. The present paper outlines a systematic study on the roll forming of a FRTP composite section using modified metal roll forming equipment and shows that useful structural sections can be produced at 10 m/min and potentially higher line speeds. The effects of various roll schedules and other process parameters on product quality are examined. It has been found that the temperature of the section at the completion of the deformation is the most significant factor in producing the desired section with high shape conformance.

A method of obtaining real time strain measurements during the deformation process is introduced, which the authors believe, offers researchers and designers a unique opportunity to understand the deformation process of FRTP sheets.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

To facilitate the experiments with FRTP composite sheets, a commercially available five-stand horizontal beam raft sheet metal roll forming machine was used. The roll former was fitted with a variable speed drive to the interconnected bottom rolls. After preliminary trials a friction drive for the top roll of each stand was installed to ensure the matching of its angular velocity with that of the bottom roll. A top hat section, Figure 3(a), was selected for this study and the initial trials were conducted using an industry standard flower pattern (flower A, Figure 2) for producing this section in aluminium alloy or mild steel. A second flower pattern (flower B, Figure 2) was also investigated, both roll configurations having a constant driving diameter for top and bottom rolls. To enable the FRTP sheet to be formed, a pre-heating oven was positioned on wheels close to the first stage and in line with the centreline of the roll former. The FRTP sample was placed on a Mylar film (to prevent adhesion to the pre-heater) in a drawer mechanism which was constructed in a way so that it also served as a feed guide for the roll former.

Roll Station	Flower A		Flower B	
	α°	β°	α°	β°
1	25	0	30	0
2	47	21	47	21
3	67	48	67	48
4	81	76	90	90
5	90	90	90	90

Figure 2. Roll station flower diagrams

The roll forming experiments were performed using Plytron™ [a continuous unidirectional glass fibre (v/v 35%)/polypropylene (PP) prepreg] laminates consolidated from four plies of the prepreg sheet, giving a nominal thickness of 2 mm. The laminates were consolidated at 180°C for 20 minutes under a 6 kPa vacuum. Test specimens were cut to 1000 mm × 90 mm where the control axis was aligned with the longitudinal axis. Average fibre misalignment was measured to be ± 0.5° from the desired orientation. A summary of the experimental variables are given in Table 1.

To enable the temperature of the FRTP strip to be measured during the preheating stage and subsequent roll forming operation, a fine 0.75 mm K-type thermocouple wire was consolidated in the centre core between the second and third layers along the laminate centreline with the hot junction at a depth of 200 mm from the leading edge. An optical sensor was placed prior to the first stage of the roll former which enabled the position and speed of the strip to be measured throughout the process. The optical sensor was triggered by strips of aluminium foil attached to the upper surface of the test sample at measured intervals. The outputs from the thermocouple and the optical sensor were processed on an Apple LC III, running Labview™ software. This setup enabled easy and accurate measurement of the temperature, speed and position of the sample.

Table 1. Experimental variables

Entry temperature:	170°C, 160°C, 150°C, 140°C, 130°C
Line Speed:	5 m/min, 10 m/min
Laminate architecture:	[±15] _{2S} , [±30] _{2S} , [±45] _{2S} , [0/90] _{2S} , [90/0] _{2S}
Cooling method:	Ambient, forced air, water spray.

In order to study the influence of various roll forming parameters, they were examined individually while the other variables were kept constant. An optimum temperature was determined which was used for all subsequent trials. The second series of trials investigated the influence of laminate architecture. The effect of roll forming line speed was then examined and subsequently a second roll schedule was trialed with the previously found optimum parameters. A simple cooling ring, which consisted of a coiled perforated copper tube through which the cooling agent was passed under pressure, was installed at the exit side of stage 5. This cooling ring was then positioned between stage 4 and 5 for use with the second roll schedule. For all tests the same preheating sequence was used, namely the sample was preheated to and held for 5 min at 175°C then cooled in a controlled manner to the desired entry temperature and fed into the roll forming machine.

Figure 3. Top hat section used for this study, with definition of deviation from intended geometry δ .

All the roll formed samples were then compared for conformity to the desired geometrical shape, Figure 3(a), in accordance with the normal procedures for roll formed sections. The deviation from intended formed angle δ is defined in Figures 3(b) and (c). A negative value for δ is universally referred to in sheet forming as spring-back and hence a positive value of δ can be termed as negative spring-back or spring-forward. The extent of curvature was measured as the amount of offset over the span length. With the condition of the fibres being an important consideration in FRTP composite structures, a visual inspection was made of the laminate to establish the degree of out-of-plane fibre buckling and in-plane fibre wrinkling.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In any forming operation involving FRTP composites, the forming temperature is invariably an important factor and traditionally the forming operation has been performed at temperatures above the T_m of the matrix material (160°C for PP). From complementary research by the authors [11,12] it has been shown that PP based Plytron™ is capable of being formed at temperatures well below T_m providing the sample has been heated above T_m and then formed before the polymer matrix is able to reach its maximum degree of crystallinity. This is best illustrated by a Differential Scanning Calorimetry diagram (DSC), shown in Figure 4 [13]. Here a definite peak is seen on heating at 160°C (indicating T_m) at which point the PP matrix is molten. Upon cooling from the melt (cooling curve in Figure 4) recrystallisation begins at T_1 (approximately 125°C) and is completed at T_2 (approximately 95°C). During this stage the PP matrix is in a super-cooled liquid phase. This recrystallisation from the melt phenomenon allows a large processing window, of nearly 60°C below T_m for PP, which to the authors' knowledge has not previously been recognised or used advantageously.

Figure 4. DSC heating and cooling curves for Plytron 35% v/v glass/PP from [14]

The roll forming operation is particularly suited to exploiting this material property, being a deformation process performed in multiple stages over a relatively long deformation time. With this in mind a simple one dimensional mathematical model was developed to predict the temperature of the FRTP strip as it passed through the various stages of the roll former. This was achieved by using a finite difference approximation to the heat diffusion equation to yield an explicit numerical solution. From this model it was able to be shown that for the range of inlet temperatures and line speeds chosen for the study, the FRTP sample was within the desired processing window. This numerical model, whilst simple, gave meaningful results when compared with the experimentally obtained temperatures.

While interpreting the results of the forming trials at various inlet temperatures it became apparent that the reliability of the process should be a major consideration. For samples formed at an inlet temperature of 160°C and above, there was approximately a 60% failure to complete the pass through all stages of the roll former. This was considered to be due to the relatively low stiffness of the composite caused by a lower viscosity of the molten matrix above T_m , resulting in the composite being unstable during the process. Conversely those strips formed at an inlet temperature below 135°C also had a high failure rate (approximately 50%) but this was found to be due to practical difficulties in supplying test pieces at a temperature close to the recrystallisation temperature of PP to the roll former. However, for samples formed at inlet temperatures of 150°C and 140°C a much lower failure rate was accounted (typically < 5%). All samples that were successfully roll formed were checked for conformance to the desired geometry, the results of this are shown in Table 2. A visual rating out of 10 was given for the

extent of in-plane fibre wrinkling of each sample with a high score being a significant presence of wrinkling. From these results it is evident that a larger scatter of formed geometry exists for those samples formed at temperatures other than at an inlet temperature of 140 C. Based on this it was decided that the preferred roll forming inlet temperature for this study would be 140 C.

Table 2. Conformance measurements at various inlet temperatures.
Line speed 5 m/min, flower A, laminate $[\pm 15]_{2S}$.

Temperature (°C)	$\delta^\circ F_1/\text{Web} (^\circ)$	$\delta^\circ F_2/F_1 (^\circ)$	Offset (mm/m)	Fibre Wrinkling
170	+3 to -3	-5 to -15	2.0	3
160	+2 to -2	-5 to -10	0.8	2
150	+2 to -2	-10 to -15	0.6	1
140	+1 to -1	-10 to -15	0.5	1
130	+3 to -3	-10 to -15	-6.0	4

The degree of in-plane wrinkling was greater at the higher inlet temperatures which the authors believe is symptomatic of lower than desirable matrix viscosity. The relatively high rating for wrinkling at 130 C was given for the presence of out-of plane buckling present particularly in the flange 1 (F_1)/flange 2 (F_2) bend regions indicating delamination. The presence of buckling in this region may be a result of lower sample temperature due to its proximity to the strip edge. However, from temperatures given by thermocouples situated in the middle of each flange there was no discernible temperature gradient measured across the sample. It was observed during the trials that for all samples there was a considerable amount of relaxation after each stage of the roll former and an appreciable amount of spring-back between F_1 and F_2 after exiting the roll former. This spring-back is contrary to the normal experience of spring-forward in FRTP bends [14]. A possible cause for this may be due to a large temperature gradient through the thickness of the sample caused by the insulating effect of the Mylar film attached to the bottom (or outer) surface. From the temperature readings it was found that for all inlet temperatures studied, the exit temperature of the sample was such that the matrix was still in a molten phase ie recrystallisation had not begun or was incomplete. Because of this high exit temperature the samples were still in a deformable state and it became clear that it would be desirable to ensure the sample was in a crystallised condition upon completion of the forming operation. To facilitate this a cooling method was employed after stage 5 and the trials were repeated. The results are given in Table 3, where the relevant details for a roll formed aluminium strip are also given.

Table 3. Conformance measurements at various temperatures.
Line speed 5 m/min, flower A, laminate $[\pm 15]_{2S}$, water cooling.

Temperature (°C)	$\delta^\circ F_1/\text{Web} (^\circ)$	$\delta^\circ F_2/F_1 (^\circ)$	Offset (mm/m)	Fibre Wrinkling
170	+5 to +10	-5 to -12	2	3
160	+4 to -3	-5 to -10	1.5	2
150	+6 to -2	-6 to -10	1.5	1
140	+1 to -1	-8 to -12	1	1
130	+1 to +3	-8 to -15	1.1	4
Aluminium Alloy	0 to -1	+1 to -1	2.7	NA

Due to this introduction of cooling some improvement in the formed geometry was achieved but still a large variation was present. The amount of relaxation in F_1/F_2 region is evidently reduced while the amount of spring forward at web/ F_1 is noticeably increased, particularly at the higher forming temperatures. However, from the temperature history it was also evident that the samples (for all inlet temperatures) were still semi-molten and hence deformable after exiting the cooling stage, indicating the cooling to be insufficient.

Figure 5. Sample temperature profile during roll forming operation with cooling facility between stage 4 and 5, flower B, line speed 5 m/min, laminate $[\pm 15]_{2S}$

From these trials the conclusion was made that the exit temperature of the sample from the roll former was the most significant factor in producing the desired shape conformity. To this end an alternative roll schedule was determined (flower B, Figure 3). For this schedule stage 1 was increased from 25° to 30° but more significantly stage 4 was changed to match stage 5 with the cooling ring now positioned between stages 4 and 5. The rationale for this was to cool the sample while being held in the intended geometry until the recrystallisation process had completed. Two cooling media (water spray and pressurised air) were investigated and the results are shown in Table 4, which also includes results for a sample formed at 10 m/min. It is clearly evident that samples formed with the water spray cooling between stages 4 and 5 have improved conformance to the intended geometry with a lower range of deviation. These results are expected if the sample temperatures are considered, Figure 5, where it can be seen that for the water cooling trials the exit temperature (roll 5) is 100°C and recrystallisation has been completed (see Figure 4). For the sample formed at 10 m/min the results can be explained considering the higher exit temperature; this shows that higher line speeds are possible provided the temperature is correctly managed. It must be noted that in using flower B roll schedule the deformation process is completed in four stages allowing a greater degree of deformation at stage 1 possible than what would be practical in roll forming metallic sheets.

Table 4 Conformance measurements with various cooling mediums.
Line speed 5 m/min (* 10 m/min), flower B, laminate $[\pm 15]_{2S}$,
inlet temperature 140 C.

Cooling medium	$\delta F_1/\text{Web} (\text{°})$	$\delta F_2/F_1 (\text{°})$	Offset (mm/m)	Wrinkling score
None	+2 to -2	-6 to +12	1	1
Pressurised air 22	+2 to +5	-6 to -9	1.5	1
Water spray 39	0 to -2	-2 to +5	0	1
Pressurised air*	0 to -2	-2 to +5	0	1

It is generally recognised that when thermoforming FRTP sheets, the fibre orientation has a large influence on part quality [15]. So having determined an appropriate roll schedule and temperature regime for the roll forming of Plytron, various laminate architectures were tried to investigate this effect with the results shown in Table 5. Of particular interest are the ratings for in-plane fibre wrinkling where a definite trend is seen, namely an increase in the presence of wrinkling with an increase in the fibre angle of the outer laminae. The wrinkling is typically located on the inner radius of a bend where compressive strains are to be expected and most notably on the inner surface of the web. For the $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ and $[0/90]_{2S}$ out-of-plane buckling was evident on the inner radius of F_1/F_2 suggesting possible delamination. To determine the initiation point of wrinkling in the various samples, laminates were halted within the roll former and allowed to cool to room

temperature thus enabling an “instantaneous view” of the semi-continuous process. While there was clearly relaxation occurring within the samples during cooling to room temperature, the method gave an indication of the deformation at each stage. The initiation of fibre wrinkling occurred at an earlier stage of the deformation process for laminates with a higher fibre angle, for example at stage 1 for $[90/0]_{2S}$, stage 2 for $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ laminate and stage 3 for $[\pm 30]_{2S}$.

Table 5. Conformance measurements for various laminates.
Line speed 5 m/min, flower B, inlet temperature 140 C, pressurised air cooling.

Laminate	$\delta F_1/\text{Web} (\%)$	$\delta F_2/F_1 (\%)$	Offset (mm/m)	Wrinkling score
$[\pm 15]_{2S}$	+2 to +5	-6 to -9	1.5	1
$[\pm 30]_{2S}$	+2 to +4	-4 to -9	2.4	4
$[\pm 45]_{2S}$	+0 to +2	-6 to -11	1	6
$[0/90]_{2S}$	+3 to +5	-4 to -7	1.8	0.5
$[90/0]_{2S}$	+2 to +5	-7 to -12	2.2	8

A desirable feature of the roll forming process is the ability to perform secondary operations during the forming process, one of these being the production of controlled longitudinally curved sections. To test the applicability of this feature to FRTP roll forming a series of trials were conducted to form curved sections with a longitudinal 1m radius and the results are given in Table 6. Notably the laminates with high fibre orientations were able to be curved with a higher degree of success while the $[\pm 15]_{2S}$ laminate exhibited gross out-of-plane buckling in F_1 and F_2 , this was rated in the same manner as in-plane wrinkling. The authors believe that these results could be significantly improved by using the more conventional method of controlling roll heights rather than a simple wooden former used in this study.

Table 6. Conformance measurements for curved sections 1-m radius.
Line speed 5 m/min, flower B, inlet temperature 140 C, pressurised air cooling.

Laminate	$\delta F_1/\text{Web} (\%)$	$\delta F_2/F_1 (\%)$	Buckling	Wrinkling score
$[\pm 15]_{2S}$	immeasurable	immeasurable	9	1
$[\pm 30]_{2S}$	+6 to +12	-3 to -5	2	4
$[\pm 45]_{2S}$	-2 to +5	-5 to -10	1	5

From these experiments it is clear that fibre instability is related to the degree of compressive stress in the fibres, which is supported by Martin et al. [15]. In order to quantify the amount of strain during the roll forming process real time strain measurement experiments were conducted. This was achieved by a novel technique of bonding electrical resistant strain gauges onto fibre bundles arranged in a ribbon form. These ribbons were then consolidated, with the appropriate electrical connections, into the laminate with the fibre ribbon aligned with the fibres in the outer lamina. The samples were then roll formed at the already established conditions and real time

Figure 6. Longitudinal membrane strain of $[0/90]_{2S}$ laminate as a function of position within roll former measured at the interface of laminae 1/2 and 3/4. Inlet temperature 140 C, line speed 5 m/min, no cooling.

strain measurements were recorded. An example of a typical strain profile is shown for a $[0/90]_{2S}$ laminate in Figure 6. This strain profile is in reasonable agreement with Zhu's [16] measurements for sheet metals at similar deformations. In the interest of brevity the full details of this method are not given here, but are the subject of a forthcoming paper [17]. This method of real time strain measurement in molten FRTP composites is of invaluable use to the manufacturing personnel, as it enables for the first time in-situ strain measurement during the deformation of FRTP sheets.

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